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**ROLE OF TEACHERS IN SOCIAL CHANGE: A STUDY
WITH REFERENCE TO SOCIAL WORK TEACHERS**

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Introduction

In recent years there has been a growing tendency towards change in all the spheres of society. In this ever-changing world there is nothing, which is static or not subject to any change. In India, villagers are subjected to change in many ways and in fact they have been undergoing changes since independence. These changes have touching and stressing impact on social, economic, political and cultural lives of the rural people. It cannot be denied that there is only a predominant cause or factor, i.e., education which is related to any change. Therefore, it may be noted that education plays a vital role in bringing about change in society from traditional to modern status.

Education is the agent or instrument for social change. Education as it stands for itself, elevate a given set of situation into a new level of state with significant change. It awakens the human consciousness into higher state and results in bringing change; a state where standard of human understanding alters or modify into transforming setting.

Social change occurs when humans edification are enhanced through different kinds of educative vehicles or agencies. Nevertheless, human edification by oneself in isolation cannot impact a social change because education for social change is a process of mutual interaction. Shared interface in a social set up involves cultures of that given situation. And therefore, a thorough study is required to see how educative elements creep into society and bring change: a social change.

After independence, the Constitution adopted by the Govt. of India has declared all citizens to be equal and the government also provided scope to the rural people to choose any form of education and professional training. In the contemporary period, because of impact of industrialization and westernization, the society as a whole and consequently the pattern of education has largely been changed. The aim of education is to facilitate the people for adjustment of changing society. The aims of education are based upon a conception of human nature, and they aim at attaining certain permanent goals. Indeed, education socializes the individuals and this provides them with the ability to adjust in the society. It also develops individual's personality so that he can challenge the evils of society and also suggest remedial measures. Thus education may give birth to leaders, reformers and revolutionary thinkers.

Review of Literature

Weber (1946 : p-426) has emphasized on the educational system and points out that “the attempt rationally to transmit to the individual certain traits, to train him for specific skills by challenging him to think and act independently – which is generally characteristic of educational spheres of rational bureaucratic organizations”. Thus according to Weber the principal aim of modern education is to develop rational faculties of human beings so that they can have independent thinking and their actions are not governed by any stereotype norms and principles. This type of training helps the individual to challenge the dogmatic beliefs and to inculcate rational thinking.

Myrdal (1968 : p-1541) in his book “Asian Drama : An Enquiry into the Poverty of Nations” points out “the more elaborate models all reduce investment in man to one factor, education”.

Dube (1974) in his paper “Modernization and Education” pointed out that through modern education the motivation of the people may be changed. Dube emphasized on the psychological aspect of education. Further, education may help in the formulation of new set of values. Finally, education will help in the development of complex organization. To run the government, to recruit people etc. education is very essential. As matters stand today though change finds its entry in rural India, yet even today a large number of villagers have remained backward and they are educationally also not well advanced. Still vast majority of the farmers is not using latest agricultural techniques in their agricultural operation, and as such the output on the whole is very meagre. Most of the villages located in isolated areas are deprived of road and facility of electricity, water supply and communication.

As regards to the changes of the villages **Altekar (1956; P.124)** has mentioned that “a village life to a great extent remains the same, people still till their lands and sow their crops in the old manner, but even here the changes are coming and coming fast enough. The theory, therefore, that the Indian village communities do not change, is completely disproved by the teaching of history”. It needs no explanation to highlight the fact that village is the unit of the rural society. It is the theatre wherein the quantum of rural life unfolds itself and functions. In this regards, like every social phenomenon the village is a historical category.

Desai (1969 : P.14) remarks that “the student of rural society should study the village, the basic unit of rural society as it originated, and underwent a constant state of development and change due to the action of its own developing internal forces as also due to its interaction with other societies”. The increasing spread of modern education among the rural people because of the establishment of schools and other educational institutions is one of the very effective means to bring about change in the rural life and structure.

Education and social change are two different concepts. In India, the changes have been taking place in the rural areas due to the impact of various measures of the Union Government. So, Indian society has been experiencing one of its greatest traditions in history since the advent of the British rule. In fact, village economic structure and institutional frame-work are based on

caste and the joint family systems. But its technological framework, economic system, social framework (caste, kinship and joint family system etc.), political organization, ideological orientation and cultural value system have been undergoing a qualitative transformation.

Objectives

- To examine the role of social work teachers in making students pro-social.
- To know the role played by social work teachers in bringing social change.
- To know whether the students have developed societal consciousness.
- To understand strategy used by social work teachers to enable all round development of students.
- To know how social work teachers motivate youth towards social change.

Methodology

In this study, the researcher adopted the scientific methodology from the selection of the problem of research to obtaining of data and generalization. Researcher selected the topic ‘Role of Teachers in Social Change: A Study with reference to Social Work Teachers’ and the study was conducted in Udupi district. Udupi and Kundapura taluks were selected in Udupi. 50 respondents were selected on the basis of purposive and snow ball sampling. Primary data were collected from the field by interview schedule to the respondents and secondary data were collected from various books, journals, Government reports.

Analysis and Interpretation

Discussions related to social change

Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that in their teaching method they give major priority for discussions related to social change. Classroom atmosphere plays productive role in enhancing students thinking and perception level and also makes them to develop critical thinking skills. While teachers give major priority to induce the concept of social change in their teaching methods then it will be more useful in moulding students personality.

Impact of field work practicum

Majority 47 (94%) of respondents have said that field work practicum makes student to explore the society. Field work practicum unveils the various phases of society and makes students to know more about it. Field work practicum makes the students to understand the society in depth and also gives them a platform to cultivate social consciousness.

Classroom atmosphere and interpersonal relationship

Majority 41 (82%) of respondents have said that classroom atmosphere is equally significant in making students to develop interpersonal relationship. When teachers take necessary steps to make their classroom interactive students will be benefited to a larger extent. Activity oriented teaching always bears fruits.

Education as agent of social change

Majority 48 (96%) of respondents have said that education is the agent or instrument for social change. Education makes youth to understand the problems in society and also makes them to establish cause effect relationship. Social work teachers should always make their class equipped with necessary information which will help their students to develop strong perception level and also critical thinking and respond towards society.

Education awakens human consciousness

Majority 45 (90%) of respondents have said that education awakens the human consciousness into higher state and results in bringing change. Education also makes youth to undergo self actualization and also evaluate themselves and inculcate necessary skills required to develop pro social personality.

Contribution of field work conference

Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that counseling contributes towards making students to understand about a cause which is needed to be handled in a best possible way. Field work conference creates a platform for establishing rapport between students and teachers and also makes students to unlock their potential.

Role of education in nation building

Majority 43 (86%) of respondents have said that education has always played an important role in the task of building an enlightened, strong and prosperous nation. Since majority of developing countries focus on empowerment of youth due to their percentage in total population, youth should be exposed to necessary education in order to make them to empowered and thus help in nation building.

Role of social work education

Majority 40 (80%) of respondents have said that social work education has played major role in making students to come across noble ideals of humanity. Since social work education makes students to introspect and also makes them to develop rational thinking, which is major ingredient for social change.

Social work teachers play major role in bringing attitudinal change

Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that social work teachers play significant role in initiating attitudinal change in students. Social work teachers can mould their students by establishing effective rapport both during classes and also during field work conferences.

Opinion about present educational system

Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that they support present educational system. Present educational system is comprised of those things which are needed for students to become a major contender in competitive market.

Spread of education in villages leads to social change

Majority 33 (66%) of respondents have said that spread of education in villages leads to social change. Village system is having few rigid practices which are blindly practiced without any logical thinking and also without valid reasons. Spread of education provides them an opportunity to introspect and decide which things should be followed and which shouldn't.

Social work education and social change in social institutions

Majority 34 (68%) of respondents have said that education brings change in social institutions viz., family, caste, marriage and religion. Education can empower individuals. Social institutions will be effective while they have a strong foundation or base of education. Education can strengthen social institutions.

Attitude towards female education

Majority 46 (92%) of respondents have said that they support female education since it is playing crucial role in bringing social change. Females should get education in order to make them empowered. Education also plays important role in making her independent and also strive for a healthy society and also build an awareness in her family.

Social work education and sense of belongingness

Majority 32 (64%) of respondents have said that social work education creates sense of belongingness among youth towards society and it creates we feeling. Social work provides ample of opportunity for youth to know and understand each other. It amplifies their voice of societal development and also helps in building a strong bond between them. Professional social work lays emphasis on giving self respect to each other and says that each individual is important. It enriches the concept of oneness and we feeling.

Awareness regarding agriculture

Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that while teaching they spread awareness regarding agriculture and try to motivate youth to build interest in agriculture. While teachers hesitate to speak about rural aspects then students also start neglecting and loose interest to discuss about such things. Teachers play pivotal role in making their students to inculcate interest about agriculture. Making youth to turn back towards agriculture is a major social change which will bear fruits.

Relationship between caste and politics

Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that caste and politics are not interrelated. Social change happens when people cast their vote without the influence of the caste which is represented by the contenders. But from the beginning caste and politics are said to be two faces of the same coin. This view should not be supported. Social work believes that caste has nothing to do with politics. Respondents said that ability and track record of the contender plays significant role in choosing the person.

Political participation of women and social change

Majority 26 (52%) of respondents have said that education can be a potent force to inspire the women folk for political participation which in turn can contribute to social change. Women will become more empowered if she is being exposed to certain level of education. If women is brought into societal mainstream by providing her opportunity to contest in elections like Panchayat Raj and higher level, she will play major role in maximizing societal development which will lay emphasis to social change.

Social work education and savings

Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that education plays an important role in arousing the idea of saving money among the youth. Youth, if inculcate the habit of engaging in social work they will become thrifty and will develop pro social mindset and also will be away from social evils. This in turn will make them socio-economically sound.

Major Findings

- Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that in their teaching method they give major priority for discussions related to social change.
- Majority 47 (94%) of respondents have said that field work practicum makes student to explore the society.
- Majority 41 (82%) of respondents have said that classroom atmosphere is equally significant in making students to develop interpersonal relationship.
- Majority 48 (96%) of respondents have said that education is the agent or instrument for social change. Education makes youth to understand the problems in society and also makes them to establish cause effect relationship.
- Majority 45 (90%) of respondents have said that education awakens the human consciousness into higher state and results in bringing change.
- Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that counseling contributes towards making students to understand about a cause which is needed to be handled in a best possible way.
- Majority 43 (86%) of respondents have said that education has always played an important role in the task of building an enlightened, strong and prosperous nation.
- Majority 40 (80%) of respondents have said that social work education has played major role in making students to come across noble ideals of humanity.

- Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that social work teachers play significant role in initiating attitudinal change in students.
- Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that they support present educational system.
- Majority 33 (66%) of respondents have said that spread of education in villages leads to social change.
- Majority 34 (68%) of respondents have said that education brings change in social institutions viz., family, caste, marriage and religion.
- Majority 46 (92%) of respondents have said that they support female education since it is playing crucial role in bringing social change.
- Majority 32 (64%) of respondents have said that social work education creates sense of belongingness among youth towards society and it creates we feeling.
- Majority 30 (60%) of respondents have said that while teaching they spread awareness regarding agriculture and try to motivate youth to build interest in agriculture.
- Majority 29 (58%) of respondents have said that caste and politics are not interrelated.
- Majority 26 (52%) of respondents have said that education can be a potent force to inspire the women folk for political participation which in turn can contribute to social change.
- Majority 35 (70%) of respondents have said that education plays an important role in arousing the idea of saving money among the youth.

Conclusion

The principal aim of the present study was to examine the role of teachers in bringing social change among youth. The basic assumption is that education can bring change in the attitudes of the youth towards different social institutions i.e. caste, marriage, family, and religion, age old agricultural practices, political participation and also in the matter of saving. Education can certainly play a decisive role in motivating the youth for giving up traditional practices and to welcome change and development. Focus was given to social work teachers in this study.

It came to know from the study that teaching method gives major priority for discussions related to social change. Social work teachers play significant role in initiating attitudinal change in students and also they play major role in creating sense of belongingness among youth and making them to inculcate pro social mindset. Social work teachers are having a opinion that education awakens the consciousness of youth into higher state and results in bringing social change.

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